

MADRAS

D2.5 Report on printed organic photodetectors performance

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Executive summary

Deliverable 2.5 exposes advances related to WP2 - T2.1.3. Organic photodetector (OPD) development (demo 2), T2.1.4 Thin film transistors development and T2.4 Quality control of the printed materials and devices.

Task T2.1.3 and T2.4 cover the characterisation and quality control of the printed layers comprising the OPD device and the device itself, including the inspection of film thickness and roughness by profilometry, the compatibility between layers, optical properties by UV-VIS/IR spectroscopy and electrical characterisation.

Task T2.1.4 is related to the development of thin-film transistors (TFT) test structures by TNO, consisting of an array of TFTs fabricated on polyimide (PI) films on a glass carrier. A detailed description of the selected TFT to be applied in demo 2 is reported.

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List of abbreviations

<i>Ag NW</i>	Silver nanowires
<i>AWCP</i>	Arjowiggings
<i>COC</i>	Centrum organické chemie
<i>D:A</i>	Donor:acceptor
<i>ETL</i>	Electron Transport Layer
<i>ETR</i>	eCooltra
<i>EUT</i>	Eurecat
<i>EQE</i>	External Quantum Efficiency
<i>GNK</i>	Genesink
<i>HTL</i>	Hole transport layer
<i>IGZO</i>	Indium gallium zinc oxide
<i>IME</i>	In-mould electronics
<i>INF</i>	InfinityPV
<i>ITO</i>	Indium Tin Oxide
<i>J_d</i>	Dark current
<i>MCF</i>	Microfibrillated cellulose
<i>NC</i>	Nanocellulose
<i>NP</i>	Nanoparticles
<i>OLAE</i>	Organic and large area electronics
<i>OPD</i>	Organic photodetector
<i>PAL</i>	Photoactive layer
<i>PEDOT:PSS</i>	Poly(3,4-EthyleneDiOxyThiophene) : sodium Poly(Styrene Sulfonate)
<i>PCE</i>	Power conversion efficiency
<i>PI</i>	Polyimide
<i>R_s</i>	Sheet resistance
<i>RT</i>	Room Temperature
<i>SMD</i>	Surface mount device
<i>TEM</i>	Transmission Electron Microscopy
<i>TNG</i>	Tecnopackaging
<i>TNO</i>	Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research
<i>UHF</i>	Ultra-High Frequency
<i>UPA</i>	University of Pardubice
<i>UPS</i>	Ultraviolet Photoelectron Spectroscopy
<i>UWB</i>	Ultra-WideFrequency
<i>UWL</i>	Uwinloc
<i>WO₃ or WO_x</i>	Tungsten oxide
<i>WP</i>	Work package

Introduction

Materials and production process developed in MADRAS project will be validated in two different demonstrators, including a biometric photosensor for user identification and a geotracking flexible tag for the Industry 4.0 sector.

For the first case, MADRAS focuses on developing a highly secure, high resolution, mechanically stable fingerprint readers for user authentication that will be integrated into the dashboard of a scooter from a vehicle sharing company, eCooltra. These biometric sensors in shared scooters are expected to increase the user convenience for unlocking, as well as the security level. Furthermore, it is expected to lead to a decreased amount of vandalism by the renter, which is an important factor impacting negatively the social mobility companies, both financially and environmentally.

The fingerprint sensor is based on a fully printed organic photodetector's (OPD) frontplane. Solution-based functional materials present undeniable advantages compared to inorganic counterparts such as Silicon with a reduced cost of manufacturing and low-temperature processing as well as a high conformability and flexibility. In MADRAS we are addressing the screening of existing and the development of novel solution-based functional materials, including the selection of appropriate photoactive layers and the manufacturing of new materials for charge transport layers, conducting electrodes and substrates that can withstand plastic processing.

The OPD frontplane consists of a photoactive layer/hole transport layer/transparent conducting electrode (PAL/HTL/TCE) stack. While state-of-the-art organic semiconducting materials have been applied in the PAL, MADRAS' developed materials are being used as 1) HTL based on WO_3 , PEDOT:PSS or a hybrid of both (PEDOT:PSS: WO_3), and 2) TCE based on Ag NW and/or highly conductive PEDOT:PSS.

The frontplane photodiodes are then applied on top of thin film transistor (TFT)-based imagers and are meant to be operated by state-of-the-art readout integrated circuits (ROIC), both developed by TNO. TNO is also developing a high-performance inorganic based thin-film encapsulation (TFE) to protect the OPD used in the fingerprint sensor from degradation in ambient conditions.

Finally, flexible TFT backplanes will be manufactured on an ultra-thin polyimide plastic film that must be transferred into a polymer substrate, thus enabling the thermoforming processes as well as a straightforward routing of the electronics inside the scooter through an integrated injection moulded part.

Purpose of the document

This document presents the advances related with the following tasks:

- T2.1.3 *Organic photodetector (OPD) development*
- T2.1.4 *Thin film transistors development*
- T2.4 *Quality control of the printed materials and devices.*

In this document we gather relevant data and conclusions about the best performing materials identified up to know, which will be in principle the preferred choice for the fabrication of demo 2 or their application on flexible OPD/OPV devices.

The report first covers the progress in the selection and characterisation of the PAL, HTL and TCE layers for the OPD device. Then, the main performance metrics of the different OPDs are shown. The process compatibility between the TFE and the OPD stack is also presented. Finally, the progress in the development of the TFT backplane is detailed.

1. Characterisation of selected layers for OPD device

This section summarises the selection and characterisation of an appropriate photoactive layer and the developed materials in MADRAS to serve in charge transport layers, conducting electrodes and substrates that can withstand the plastic processing conditions.

1.1 Characterisation of PAL layers

Photoactive materials that outperform currently used materials must be employed to realise fully solution-processed OPD that reach the required performance for detection. Indeed, the use of printed electrodes commonly entails a reduction in efficiency that needs to be compensated.

Consequently, a thorough study on the most suitable photoactive material system for OPD was conducted during the first period of execution of WP2. As a result from the screening study, three donor:acceptor (D:A) blends - PTQ10:Y6, PTQ10:Y12 and PTQ10:IDIC-, were chosen as the preferred candidate systems to be used in MADRAS project. The three systems show a broad and strong absorption in the visible and near infrared range (Figure 1), therefore fulfilling the requirements for the fingerprint sensor.

Figure 1. UV-Vis absorbance spectra of PAL of the selected blends PTQ10:Y6 (left), PTQ10:Y12 (middle) and PTQ10:IDIC (right) at increasing thicknesses from 30 to 350 nm, as indicated with the black arrows.

The solution-processing of the PAL by means of doctor blade (similar to slot-die coating) allows the deposition of smooth and homogeneous layers with controlled thickness. For instance, fine tuning of the processing conditions allows fabricating PTQ10:IDIC layers with layers of thicknesses around 250 nm and higher (Figure 2), which is a requirement to attain low dark currents in the OPD devices.

Figure 2. Optical microscopy images of a PTQ10:IDIC layer and profilometry (right) of the ZnO/PAL stack.

1.2 Characterisation of PEDOT:PSS:WO₃ layers

1.2.1 Electrical characterisation of PEDOT:PSS:WO₃ layers

GNK reported in D1.3 and D1.6 the synthetic development and formulation of hybrid inks based on WO₃ nanoparticles combined with organic semi-conducting polymers such as PEDOT:PSS. The use of such polymer enhanced the conductivity of the HTL ink formulation without impacting the particle size. Other studies were carried out by GNK such as the reproducibility of the synthesis of hybrid PEDOT:PSS:WO₃ and the use of different grades of PEDOT:PSS (especially the one from the partner COC). The summary of the performance is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of the characteristics of the neat and hybrid PEDOT:PSS:WO₃ nanoinks and 3-layer coating performances (NM: not measurable, Ø: diameter, R: electrical resistance, Ra/Rq: roughness, Thick.: thickness, ρ: electrical resistivity and c: electrical conductivity)

Synthesis n°	Ligand A	PEDOT:PSS Conc.	Hybrid NPs Ø in ink (nm)	Ink viscosity @20 °C (mPa.s)	R (MΩ)	Ra/Rq (nm)	Thick. (nm)	ρ (Ω.cm)	c (10 ⁻² S/cm)
Synthesis for SW41014 Commercial ink	10 ± 3%	/	8 ± 3	2	NM	2/2.5	210	/	/
MAD_Synt1 MAD-W-dev1	/	14%	23	6.5	0.3	25/35	350	26.3	3.8
MAD_Synt2 MAD-W-dev2	/	9%	36	5.4	0.9	60/80	210	47.3	2.1
MAD_Synt3 MAD-W-dev4	/	12%	45	6.5	0.2	70/100	250	12.5	8.0
MAD_Synt5 MAD-W-dev8	6%	6%	68	5.7	0.6	75/110	230	34.5	2.9
MAD_Synt6 MAD-W-dev9	4.6%	9.2%	160	5.5	0.3	90/120	210	15.8	6.3
MAD_Synt10&11 MAD-W-dev11	/	14%	42	13	0.2	12/17	170	8.5	11.8
MAD_Synt12 MAD-W-dev12	5%	5%	55	6.7	0.3	2/5	190	14.3	7.0

1.2.2 Optical and morphological characterisation of PEDOT:PSS:WO₃ layers

The optimised formulation of the acidic binder-free hybrid ink (see D1.6) enabled the coating of homogeneous HTL on top of the PAL. However, as seen in Figure 3, the 100 nm thick HTL presents a rather rough topography.

Figure 3. Optical microscopy images of a PEDOT:PSS:WO₃ layer and profilometry (right) of the ZnO/PAL/PEDOT:PSS:WO₃ stack.

Although this surface roughness does not harm the functionality of the device (see section 2), the resulting light scattering affects the visual appearance of the stack. Indeed, the transmittance of the stack in the visible range drops significantly upon addition of the HTL, especially in the 380 - 550 nm range (Figure 4). This aspect will be addressed in the coming months.

Figure 4. Transmittance spectra of the ZnO/PAL and ZnO/PAL/HTL stack.

1.3 Characterisation of PEDOT:PSS layers

1.3.1 Electrical characterisation of PEDOT:PSS layers

For the evaluation of electronic properties of PEDOT:PSS layers, various characteristics as conductivity, work function and charge carrier mobility have been evaluated. Considering that the functionality of the HTL layer is a multiparametric aspect, different characteristics have been studied, as follows.

1.3.1.1 Conductivity

One of the most important parameters is the conductivity, which is estimated for every new ink formulation. The development of various PEDOT:PSS ratio inks and the use (or absence) of dopants have yielded a wide range of conductivity values.

Table 2. Main conductivity characteristics of PEDOT:PSS films using PINK formulations

Ink #	Conduc tive polyme r	Ratio	Without secondary dopant			With 5 % of Ethylene glycol			
			Dry layer thickn ess [nm]	Sheet resista nce [Ohm]	Conduc tivity [S/cm]	Ink #	Dry layer thickn ess [nm]	Sheet resista nce [Ohm]	Conduc tivity [S/cm]
PINK 169	PEDOT: PSS	1:1	120	2.27×10^3	36.6	PINK 176	121	8.215×10^2	100.6
PINK 170	PEDOT: PSS	1:1.4	171	2.28×10^3	25.7	PINK 177	149	5.45×10^2	123.0
PINK 171	PEDOT: PSS	1:2.5	141	8.65×10^3	8.2	PINK 178	143	7.9×10^2	88.4
PINK 172	PEDOT: PSS	1:3.5	140	2.90×10^4	2.5	PINK 179	131	1.82×10^3	41.9
PINK 173	PEDOT: PSS	1:5	169	6.07×10^4	1.0	PINK 180	132	3.79×10^3	20.0
PINK 174	PEDOT: PSS	1:15	273	5.64×10^7	6.5×10^{-4}	PINK 181	268	7.65×10^7	4.9×10^{-4}

The best performance of OPD was repeatably achieved for PEDOT:PSS 1:1.4 ratio, where the one of the best one HTL layer was based on ink PINK 221 with a conductivity of 143 S/cm. The optimised (ST) variant of PEDOT:PSS 1:1.4, that is ink PINK 283, exhibits a conductivity of 130 S/cm. These two inks will be used in next experiments for fabrication of optimised OPD devices.

Alongside the HTL usage of PEDOT:PSS layers, higher conductivity was required for TCE application in OPD. It has been observed that the developed inks based on PEDOT:PSS 1:2.5 HC dispersions are the most promising for TCE, as they offered conductivity values close to 984 S/cm (PINK 223) with AMIDE I solvent, and 634 S/cm for EG and PINK .

1.3.1.2 Work Function

The next parameter which has been evaluated for PEDOT:PSS layers is the work function, which has been measured with Ultraviolet photoelectron spectroscopy (UPS), owing to the higher reliability and repeatability as compared with Kelvin Probe.

Figure 5. Work function of various PEDOT:PSS ratios in undoped/ doped form, where the secondary dopant was EG

Figure 5 shows the data from set of ink formulations with - EG (PINK 176-181) and without secondary dopants (PINK 169 - 174). In both cases the highest level of WF was achieved with the 1:1.4 ratio and peaked at 4.64 eV (PINK 177). These results confirm the PEDOT:PSS 1:1.4 as the best candidate for HTL in the OPD in terms energy level alignment.

For the highly conductive PEDOT:PSS (1:2.5), which is meant to be used as TCE, the work function was measured at 4.41 eV.

1.3.1.3 Charge carrier mobility

The next evaluated electrical parameter is the charge carrier mobility (see D1.5 for further technical details). This parameter is measured for PEDOT:PSS layers within an OECT structure. The results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Estimated charge carrier mobility for PEDOT:PSS with various ratios

PEDOT:PSS	Dry layer thickness [nm]	C* [F cm ⁻³]	μ _{OECT} (cm ² V ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)
PEDOT/PSS 1:1	121	125	0.46
PEDOT/PSS 1:1.4	149	95	1.54
PEDOT/PSS 1:2.5	143	62	0.95
PEDOT/PSS 1:3.5	131	56	0.76
PEDOT/PSS 1:5	132	39	0.68
PEDOT/PSS 1:2.5 HC	398	57	1.36

From estimated value is found, that highest charge carrier mobility exhibited PEDOT:PSS with ratio 1:1.4. From data is the table it is clear, that 1:1.4 ratio has a peak mobility compared with other PEDOT:PSS ratios. High charge carrier mobility is also exhibited by PEDOT:PSS 1:2.5 HC, which surpass the one for its normal variant.

1.3.2 Optical and morphological characterisation of PEDOT layers

Optical and morphological properties of PEDOT:PSS layers deposited using spiral-bar coating especially possible differences caused by different secondary solvent for PEDOT:PSS ratio 1:1.4 and for different PEDOT:PSS ratios ranging from 1:1 to 1:15 were examined (PINK 176 - PINK 181). Thickness of the samples was measured by Profilometer KLA Tencor P-7. Surface roughness was calculated using the same instrument. Variable spectroscopic ellipsometer VASE (J. A. Woollam Co.) was used for the optical characterization of the prepared samples. The ellipsometer is equipped with an automatic rotating analyser over the spectral range 300 nm - 1100 nm (UV-VIS-NIR), measuring 30 revolutions with 10 nm wavelength steps at four selected angles of incidence (AOI) (50°, 55°, 60° and 55°). Normal incidence optical transmittance was measured by the same instruments. WVASE32 software was used for modelling the measured data. From fig. 1 overall good agreement between layer thickness obtained using both methods can be seen, except selected samples.

Figure 6. Comparison of layer thickness obtained by profilometry (red) and ellipsometry (black column).

From the profilometry measurement, the root mean square surface roughness was calculated as a parameter describing the surface morphology of the samples and its comparison with the surface roughness obtained from ellipsometry measurement is depicted in Figure 6 (histograms). In this case typical error for surface roughness obtained using ellipsometry is ± 2 nm. Surface roughness is first decreasing and then increasing with increasing PSS content in PEDOT:PSS (see fig. 2b) where layer with PEDOT:PSS ratio equal to 1:1.4 exhibits the lowest surface roughness.

Figure 7. Comparison of transmission measured for layers with different PEDOT:PSS ratio onto glass substrate (left) and corresponding calculated absorption coefficient (right).

Using thickness d obtained from ellipsometry and measured optical transmission absorption coefficient α which is independent on layer thickness can be calculated using equation:

$$\alpha = \frac{2.303}{d} \cdot \log \left(\frac{T_{\text{glass}}}{T_{\text{layer}}} \right) \quad (1)$$

Comparison of absorption coefficient for all samples is depicted at fig. 3. Pronounced differences visible especially for higher wavelengths are very likely caused by absorption on free carriers. Increase of PSS content leads to decrease of the absorption coefficient for higher wavelengths and is probably connected also with the change of absorption coefficient for lower wavelengths.

1.3.3 1.1.3 Mechanical characterisation of PEDOT:PSS layers

For selected type of HTL layer - PEDOT:PSS 1:1.4 the stability of the electrical conductivity of spiral bar coated PEDOT:PSS layer on PET under cyclic strain has been tested. For coating the ink formulation based on PEDOT:PSS 1:1.4 was used.

The method used to determine the variation of resistance of PEDOT:PSS 1:1.4 (as a best candidate for HTL layer) upon bending cycles consisted in characterizing upon 400 bending cycles. The testing sample (stripe cca 70 x 12 mm) was fabricated at UPA by spiral bar coating using 50 μm spiral. The samples was cut and at sides of strip the silver based ink was applied for creating of contacting pads. The experimental set up from x-y moving stage where its linear movement was programmed by g-code to make periodical movement. The sample were attached into 3D printed clamps and fastened by screws. The samples were contacted by crocodile contacts. For the measurement of resistance, the acquisition station Keithley DAQ6510 was used with acquisition time cca 43 ms. Withing bending tests for all samples TPU/print top/down orientations were proven. The obtained resistances of samples were plotted in form R/R_0 .

Figure 8. Setup of bending test of PEDOT:PSS 1:1.4, dependence of R/R_0 of layer of PEDOT:PSS 1:1.4 on stage/number of cycle.

From results of bending test it could be concluded, that for PEDOT:PSS there is small change in range of 0.05 % / 0.1% resp. within each bending cycle, which could be seen in inset of graph at Figure 8. The resistance change is higher for orientation PEDOT:PSS layer on TOP (0.1%), where is given layer little bit more stretched. After ending of bending cycle the resistance is going back to its starting level. From data clear, that there is no obvious trend within 400 cycles and value of R/R_0 didn't differ from 1 in whole range. From performed test it could be concluded, that PEDOT:PSS 1:1.4 layer is mechanically very stable.

1.4 Characterisation of AgNW layers

1.4.1 Electrical characterisation of AgNW layers

As reported in D1.1 and D1.4 deliverables, GNK has developed 2 optimised transparent conductive inks for slot die: Ink13 and Ink23. These two inks provide an enhanced conductivity (sheet resistance down to 5 Ω /sq) and improved stability over 3 months compared to the reference commercial ink. Additionally, 2 other optimised transparent conductive inks suitable for screen-printing have been developed: Ink42 and Ink93, with adequate viscosity (> 1 Pa.s at shear rate around 10 s^{-1}) and good printability. The performances of the two transparent conductive screen-printable inks have been respectively achieved as follows: (i) the sheet resistance was measured at 15 ± 5 and 20 ± 5 Ω/\square and (ii) the residency time was observed for 5 min and 10 min (Table 4).

Table 4. Summary of the AgNW-based ink properties and electrical performance after blade coating 24 μ m (for slot die) or printing (for screen-printing) on PET with similar curing conditions at RT for 90s then 120°C for 5 min (NA: Not applicable)

Ink	Printing technology	AgNW content	Viscosity @20 °C	Rs (ops)	Residency time (min)
Ink13	Slot Die	0.7	65 mPa.s (@40 s^{-1})	8.7 ± 3.3	NA
Ink23	Slot Die	0.5	50 mPa.s (@40 s^{-1})	8.6 ± 4.8	NA
Ink42	Screen-printing	0.7	1.7 ± 0.1 Pa.s (@10 s^{-1})	15 ± 5	5
Ink93	Screen-printing	0.5	1.6 ± 0.1 Pa.s (@10 s^{-1})	20 ± 5	10

1.4.2 Optical and morphological characterisation of AgNW layers

As reported in D1.1 and D1.4, the optical performances of the AgNW-based inks developed by GNK is summarised in Table 5. All the inks have high transmittance ($> 85\%$) (Figure 9) and an homogeneous appearance (Figure 10) and an homogeneous appearance (Figure 10) and an homogeneous appearance (Figure 10).

Table 5. Summary of the AgNW-based ink optical performance after blade coating 24 μ m (for slot die) or printing (for screen-printing) on PET with similar curing conditions at RT for 90s then 120°C for 5 min (NA: Not applicable)

Ink	Printing technology	AgNW content	Transmittance (@550 nm)
Ink13	Slot Die	0.7	87 ± 2 %
Ink23	Slot Die	0.5	86 ± 2 %
Ink42	Screen-printing	0.7	85 ± 4 %
Ink93	Screen-printing	0.5	86 ± 3 %

Figure 9. Transmittance (T) spectra of Ag NW layers prepared with blade coating (ink 13, ink 23) or screen-printing (ink 42, ink93) on PET with similar curing conditions: 90 s at RT, then 5 min at 120°C

Figure 10. Pictures of screen-printed samples of Ink 42 (top left) and Ink93 (top right) and microscopic photography of an Ink93 coating with x2000 magnification (bottom).

In turn, Ink 13 has been successfully implemented to build the TCE on top of the PAL/HTL stack (Figure 11). The blade coating yielded a homogeneous layer, however resembling the roughness of the underlying HTL.

Figure 11. Optical microscopy images of a Ag NW layer (from Ink13) and profilometry (right) of the ZnO/PAL/PEDOT:PSS:WO₃/Ag NW stack.

The solution-processed TCE moderately decreases the transmittance of the overall stack (Figure 12).

Figure 12. Transmittance spectra of the ZnO/PAL, ZnO/PAL/HTL and ZnO/PAL/HTL/TCE stack.

2. Organic photodetector performance

The performance specifications for the OPD on the fingerprint sensor require an EQE >50% and a dark current value in the range of 10^{-5} mA/cm² at -2V. Here, the dark currents of OPD devices using MADRAS' printed HTL and TCE have been evaluated.

2.1.1 Characterisation of reference OPD device on test structures

In view of the front plane development of Demo 2, several OPD devices were fabricated on top of TNO's test structure substrates based on materials used for TFT backplanes for the fingerprint sensors. The test structures contain MoCr and IGZO as bottom electrode and electron transport layer (ETL), respectively. A test structure schematic and the real sample appearance before and after PAL deposition and electrode evaporation are depicted in Figure 13.

Figure 13. Top row: TNO's test structure schematics and photo of a TFT backplane. Bottom row: Appearance of the deposited PAL before (left) and after (right) the deposition of the translucent MoOxAg evaporated electrode

First, thick PAL were deposited using solution-processing on the TFT back plane to validate the chosen photoactive material blend (PTQ10:IDIC). Low dark currents in the range of the targeted 10^{-5} mA/cm² have been obtained, thus validating the material choice (Figure 14).

Figure 14. Dark J-V characteristics of OPD devices using thick PAL layers built on top of the TFT backplanes

2.1.2 Characterisation of OPD devices with selected layers

In a second phase, we tried the best HTL inks developed so far to fabricate OPD devices with both the PAL and the HTL prepared with solution-processing techniques. We also tested the HTL/TCE combination. This first trial revealed that the evaporated MoO_x layer can be successfully replaced with the solution-processed hybrid PEDOT:PSS:WO₃ developed in WP1 (Figure 15). This system can still deliver the target dark current of 10⁻⁵ mA/cm² at -2 V. The complete characterisation of this device, including EQE and LBIC is currently ongoing. Further experiments will be carried out in the coming months to find a solution (i.e., to reduce the leakage) for the TCE based on Ag NW.

Figure 15. a) dark J-V characteristics of OPD devices on TFT back planes using thick PAL layers and the best HTL systems chosen so far: PEDOT:PSS (purple data), hybrid PEDOT:PSS:WO₃ (blue data) and the fully solution-processed OPD using PEDOT:PSS/Ag NWs (green data). b) The hybrid HTL achieves the target dark current values and an ON/OFF ratio greater than 1k (ON/OFF ratio at -2 V; ON values determined for indoor conditions: 0.2 suns ≈ 500 lux).

At this point of the project (M20), it has been agreed to keep using glass/ITO substrates to conduct screening and optimisation tasks, albeit this bottom electrode is unsuitable to minimise current leakage and thus low dark currents are unrealistic to be obtained. Then, as soon as a novel device stack is identified as a potential candidate to replace the evaporated layers (i.e., achieving comparable dark currents), we will transfer it to the TFT back plane.

For instance, using the screening architecture we have concluded that using the selected PTQ10:IDIC PAL and the hybrid PEDOT:PSS:WO₃ HTL in combination with the printed Ag NWs TCE, it is realistic to expect dark currents that meet the target values (Figure 16).

Figure 16. Visual appearance of two sets of OPD devices using the PTQ10:IDIC PAL with evaporated MoOx/Ag (left) or printed PEDOT:PSS:WO₃/Ag NWs (middle). The dark JV characteristics (right) reveal the potential of the fully solution-processed OPD.

The most relevant advances achieved in the period M20-M27 in regards of the selected OPD multistack materials (see also D2.3) and performance are summarised herein:

1. Photoactive layer: the final PAL material blend chosen is PM6:DTY6, because of its broader and stronger absorption (and consequently higher EQE) in comparison to PTQ10:IDIC, as well as its processability at large-scale with non-halogenated solvents. For instance, Figure 17 shows the *J-V* characteristics of OPD devices on TFT back planes using thick PAL layers comparing the two donor polymers, PTQ10 and PM6, revealing a significant improvement in the dark current and the ON/OFF ratio in the PM6:DTY6 blend. This improvement is also seen in the EQE spectra, where PM6:DTY6 surpasses by far the target minimum 50% EQE.

Figure 17. a) dark (red) and light (blue) *J-V* characteristics of OPD devices on TFT backplanes based on the PTQ10:DTY6 (left graph) and PM6:DTY6 (right graph) active layer blends, and b) their corresponding EQE spectra; the red dashed line indicates the target minimum EQE threshold.

2. Hole transport layer: The continual improvement of the hybrid PEDOT:PSS:WO₃ ink has resulted in PINK361 as the selected HTL material for Demo 2. Its homogeneous coating as well as its performance have been validated in several runs of devices, at TNO and EUT in parallel.

Figure 18. J-V characteristics of OPD devices on TFT backplanes using PM6:DTY6 as the active layer, PINK361 as the HTL, and ink13 as the AgNWs top electrode, validated both at EUT and at TNO.

3. Transparent top electrode: A thorough study has been performed to identify the best possible AgNWs formulation, including changes in the Ag NW concentration as well as in the additive content. The conclusion is that ink13 is the best suited ink for the deposition of the transparent top electrode in Demo 2.

The whole OPD stack has been therefore validated in terms of performance, reaching the target values (dark current, ON/OFF ratio, and EQE).

In addition, the printability of these inks at real Demo 2 size has been validated by slot-die coating:

Figure 19. Validation of the printability of the selected inks for Demo 2 fabrication by means of slot-die coating.

3. Thin film transistor development

This section is related to task T2.1.4 consisting of the development of thin-film transistors (TFTs) used for the backplanes on polyimide for the fingerprint biometric reader.

The schematic layout of a dual-gate transistor is shown in Figure 20. From top to bottom, the transistor consists of the top gate, top insulator, the semiconductor with source and drain electrodes, the bottom gate dielectric and finally the bottom gate. The specifications and fabrication process are described in deliverable D3.1 section 3.2.

Figure 20. Cross-section of dual-gate a-IGZO TFT on flexible polyimide substrate.

During Madras and more specifically, during the first TFT test structures run, the Plasma Enhanced Chemical Vapour Deposition (PECVD) tool at an external facility on the High Tech Campus in Eindhoven that was used for the Holst Centre TFT fabrication broke down and it was decided by the external facility not to have it repaired. In parallel Holst Centre had purchased its own PECVD tool for the fabrication of TFTs. When the schematic in Figure 20 is considered, the PECVD tool is used for:

- SiN barrier on top of polyimide,
- the first SiO₂ gate insulator,
- the second SiO₂ gate insulator on top of the IGZO,
- and the so-called inter-metal dielectric with SiN.

All of these layers have an effect on the TFT performance and can result in many different effects on TFT performance, such as poorly functioning dielectrics that cause random shorts during TFT operation, an over doping of IGZO in the TFT channel resulting in transistors that are always on and non-functional, a poor doping of the IGZO outside the channel resulting in TFTs that do not turn on, or with a heavily shifted threshold voltage outside any useful operational window. Contrary to expectations, so far all fabrication efforts, process optimizations, and equipment improvements have not resulted in a reliable and reproducible TFT process on foil. On glass it was possible to demonstrate functional TFTs as expected. The addition of PI/SiN as a substrate will change the processes conditions due to the effect of doping on IGZO by the SiN barrier on PI, but the combination of the irreproducibility of the process conditions during deposition and the variations in the system over time, resulted thus far in an unsuccessful attempt for a TFT process on foil.

During all the process optimizations, to speed up the iterations and perhaps the route to reliable TFTs on foil, a different TFT architecture was introduced; a single gate TFT on AlO_x. The AlO_x is deposited by spatial atomic layer deposition (s-ALD) onto the PI foil. Hence, only two layers in the TFT stack are done by the PECVD tool and influencing the TFT performance. Moreover, and equally important, the fabrication time for these TFTs is slightly shorter and due to less brittle dielectrics present in the stack with less thickness, the chance of failure due to cracking during thermoforming is reduced.

Figure 21. Schematic cross-section of the self-aligned dual-gate TFT architecture with a single-gate self-aligned TFT architecture on AlOx.

Batch (internal)	glass/foil	Plates	SG/DG	TFT Test samples	TFT sensor backplanes	functional TFTs samples	Remarks
61	foil	4	DG	48		48	1st part of TFT stack by previous PECVD tool
65	foil	4	DG		8		
66	foil	4	DG		8		
67	foil	4	SG		8		Stopped due to barrier problems
68	glass	4	SG		16	16	requires repair process for functionality
69	foil	4	DG		8		
70	foil	6	both		16	8	
71	foil	4	SG	48	24		
72	foil	4	SG	48	24		
73	glass	4	SG	24	12		
74	both	8	both	96	48		Currently in progress Oct/Nov 2022
Currently completed on foil		30		144	88		
Total started		42		168	124		
Total expected on foil		36		216	124		Including current running batch

Table 6. Overview of TFT batch runs during Madras, with the number of TFT test samples and biometric sensor backplanes indicated.

The first batch (61) that was partly completed on the previous PECVD tool was finished with the final SiN layer in the new PECVD tool. These resulted in functional TFTs and have been utilized for the lamination, thermoforming, and injection moulding experiments (Deliverable 2.4). However, a difference in reproducibility of the TFTs was observed between the TFTs in the so-called process evaluation modules (PEMs) and the TFTs in the Madras test structures: the Madras test structure TFTs were a lot less reproducible between different TFTs, suffered from variations in consecutive IV sweeps and would quite frequently short-circuit during the measurement. The difference in design is shown in Figure 22, together with an optical microscope photograph of a shorted TFT after the I-V measurement.

Figure 22. TFT design comparison between that of a TFT in the PEMs and that in the TFT test structure design. Furthermore, a microscopy image of a shorted TFT after I-V measurement.

After extensive analysis of the individual characterizations that can be performed for the different layers in the TFTs stack using the PEM test structures, it was found that the SiO₂ dielectric was leaky and out of spec. In combination with the large bottom and top gate metal overlap, this resulted in unwanted short formation during measurement. When sweeping the TFT and keeping the bottom and top gate electrode at the same voltage, the TFTs could be measured reliably and utilized for the lamination, thermoforming and injection moulding

experiments. Some examples for the TFT measurements are shown in Figure 23, where clearly the benefit of the bottom and top gate electrode at the same voltage can be seen and the difference in reproducibility with TFTs present in the PEMs.

Figure 23. TFT characteristics showing the difference in reliability between bottom and top gate electrode at the same voltage compared to bottom electrode at 0 V. The reliability of the TFTs in the PEMs is much higher due to a much smaller metal-metal overlap in the design.

Figure 24. Photograph of completed backplane in PI with bonded ICs, still on glass (A). Capacitive readout of the backplane with little variations and little amount of defect lines: a uniform readout (B). Part of the readout (capacitively) captured while touching with a finger. (C) Although only briefly an image appears, the fingerprint is very clearly distinguishable and demonstrates the backplane and biometric sensor design.

Batch run 70 resulted in 2 plates (each with 4 biometric sensor backplanes present) showed good TFT performance. One sensor backplane of each plate was bonded with readout ICs such that the backplane performance could be evaluated. One of the two sensor backplanes suffered from too many shorts present somewhere in the backplane stack, leading to an overload of the readout IC and this device could not be evaluated in terms of performance. The other samples had a very low number of defects present in the sensor backplane and showed a clear uniform capacitive readout, see Figure 24. This also demonstrates the functionality of the new sensor design introduced in Madras, with gate drivers and readout IC located on a single side of the active sensor area and where the gate drivers are controlled via the readout ICs. Moreover, since no frontplane is present and simply the charge is directly recorded, for a brief moment the fingerprint of a finger in contact could be captured, see Figure 24C. For privacy purposes

only part of the fingerprint is shown. The difference in capacitance variations where the ridges of the fingerprint touch the backplane and the valleys with an airgap between finger and backplane could be recorded. This sample was utilized for testing of the effect of lamination and thermoforming on the sensor backplane, see Deliverable 2.4. The other remaining 6 TFT backplanes are stored and will be used for frontplane with encapsulation processing and thermoforming with injection moulding finalization.

At the time of writing a TFT batch (74) is running of which the TFT results are expected in the coming weeks (11/2022). After a thorough analysis of all variations in the past, both for deposition recipes as well as for hardware changes to the PECVD system, batch 74 is expected for some of the recipes to result in functional TFTs. In case none of the plates results in functional TFT test structures and sensor backplanes, it could only mean that during the course of the current activities changes have occurred to the PECVD system that are not yet understood. A high-level fabrication overview of batch 74 is presented in Table 7 below.

SA 074 - TFT backplanes on foil						
#	dual gate	single gate	glass	foil	PECVD process 1	PECVD process 2
1	X		X		X	
2	X			X	X	
3	X			X	X	
4		X	X		X	
5		X		X	X	
6		X		X	X	
7		X		X		X
8		X		X		X

Table 7. Variations within batch 74, currently being fabricated.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

This deliverable serves as a guide for taking the decision on the selection of the final stack frontplane for the development of the fingerprint sensor within MADRAS project. The selection of the best performing materials for OPD identified up to now and relevant characterisation of the selected PAL, HTL and TCE layers are herein exposed.

Concerning the PAL, the absorption spectra of three possible photoactive material combinations are shown to demonstrate sufficient absorption in the visible and near infrared range, therefore fulfilling the requirements for the fingerprint sensor. Then, for the case of PTQ10:IDIC, which has been the most further explored PAL to be used in demo 2 during first period, optical microscopy and profilometer measurements are shown to demonstrate the homogeneity of the layers. Besides, the same characterisation is made on samples with the most promising HTL developed in MADRAS (PEDOT:PSS:WO₃) deposited on top of PAL.

In fact, the stack based on PEDOT:PSS:WO₃/Ag NW is up to now the preferred choice for the fabrication of demo 2, according to the promising OPD performances achieved. The other developed inks, mainly PEDOT:PSS and Ag NW for screen printing, have also been selected, as they will be alternatively used in the development of flexible OPD/OPV devices.

Concerning the PEDOT:PSS inks developed by UPA, a detailed characterisation regarding conductivity, work function and charge carrier mobility has been presented for several ratios in order to justify the choice of PEDOT:PSS 1:1.4 as the best HTL and PEDOT:PSS 2.5 HC as the best TCE. Additionally, quality control of the layers in terms of optical and morphological properties is carefully analysed by comparing results on absorption, profilometry and ellipsometry. The mechanical stability of PEDOT:PSS printed layers is also checked by means of cyclic bending test.

Concerning the PEDOT:PSS:WO₃ and Ag NW inks developed by GNK, a summary of the most relevant parameters, already presented in D1.1 and D1.4, is exposed. As a remark, results on the implementation of Ink 13 to build the TCE on top of the PAL/HTL stack (PTQ10:IDIC/PEDOT:PSS:WO₃) are presented. The blade coating yielded a homogeneous layer, however resembling the roughness of the underlying HTL.

Further development was performed to evaluate the applicability of the OPD front plane on demo 2. Thus, the chosen materials were deposited on top of TNO's TFT test structure substrates based on MoCr and IGZO. First, the selected PTQ10:IDIC blend was validated in its own with evaporated HTL and top electrode, delivering the lowest dark current compared with PTQ10:Y6 and PTQ10:Y12. Afterwards, the fully-printed material stack (PAL/HTL/TCE) was tested in a sequential manner. First, we demonstrated that the evaporated MoOx layer can be successfully replaced with the solution-processed hybrid PEDOT:PSS:WO₃ and still deliver the target dark current of 10⁻⁵ mA/cm². Then, we also showed that the combination of PEDOT:PSS:WO₃ with Ag NWs as solution-processed HTL/TCE has the potential to attain the target dark current values. From M19 to M27 the final PAL material blend changed to PM6:DTY6, because of its broader and stronger absorption (and consequently higher EQE) in comparison to PTQ10:IDIC, as well as its processability at large-scale with non-halogenated solvents. The homogeneous coating of all the stack layers as well as its performance have been validated in several runs of devices, at TNO and EUT in parallel.

Finally, the TFT backplane fabrication process is presented. Extensive work was performed on developing a reliable TFT process on polyimide foil using a newly installed PECVD tool. Contrary to initial expectations, so far all fabrication efforts, process optimizations, and equipment improvements have not resulted in a reliable and reproducible TFT process on foil. As an alternative, self-aligned single-gate TFT architecture on AlOx was introduced that allows for 1) a faster feedback loop since there are less layers in the stack compared to the self-aligned

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dual-gate TFT architecture and 2) for a lower dependence of the TFT performance on the layers deposited by the new PECVD tool.

At the present time, a TFT batch run is in progress with both self-aligned dual-gate and single-gate architectures, using the most promising recipes and hardware modifications to deliver the highest chance for a functional TFT outcome.

5. Risk analysis

The table presented below describes the potential risk and deviations during the project and the contingency plan that would minimize the risk related to the deliverable D2.5.

Risk description	Likelihood	Contingency plan	Who/Actions
Ag NW ink doesn't achieve the expected conductivity and transparency	Medium	Mixture of NW with NPs, curing by different techniques or tuning the thickness of the coating	GNK/Ag NPs based inks were developed for antennas applications (higher conductivity), Ag NW ink coating has been optimized to get the better compromised between transparency and conductivity.
WO _x does not achieve the expected conductivity values, mobility and transparency	Medium	Mixture with dopants, curing by different techniques	GNK/ Try to reformulate the WO ₃ nanoparticle-based ink without the acidic binder. Develop hybrid PEDOT:PSS/WO ₃ ink without such acidic binder.
New formulations of PEDOT doesn't achieve expected values for hole mobility	Medium	Mixture with dopants and reformulation with different solvents	Nothing to report.
OPD stack with printed electrodes does not reach required dark current and EQE	Medium	Use evaporated HTL and top electrodes for demo 2. HTL and conductive inks developed in MADRAS (PEDOT, hybrid, WO ₃ , AgNW) would then be applied on OPD/OPV devices using transparent CNF as substrate.	TNO/ Revise dark current requirements for application in final demo. Chose best HTL/top electrode combination for fingerprint sensor. EUT/ Develop OPD/OPV on flexible substrate using MADRAS' inks and substrates.
Low compatibility between the injection moulding material and the printed device	High	Use of rough (less transparent) NCF for application in Demo 1	Nothing to report for Demo 2.
Reproducibility of the SMD process	Medium	Redesign of the foil, reallocate the components in the optoelectronics -identify the worse scenario and check that the process is still embedding the components.	Nothing to report.
Delays in delivery of assets (all)	Low	Day to day coordination of the activities to prevent it	Nothing to report.
Unforeseen conflict between partners (IPR issues, etc) or defaulting party (all)	Low	Build professional working relationships, Signature of Consortium Agreement beforehand, with provision of legal basis for conflict resolutions or/and defaulting mechanisms.	Nothing to report.

Table 8. Risk Analysis